

From Rule of Violence to Rule of Trust? State-Society Relations in Post-Asad Syria

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The overthrow of Bashar al-Asad was a monumental rupture in Syria's history, permitting a new beginning for the country. As Syrians are rebuilding their country, the relations between the new rulers and the ruled will be redrawn. Asad-era and wartime rule relied heavily on violence and coercion. Asad's fall had raised hopes that those practices would be over, and a new social contract based on trust could emerge. Now, more than half a year since Asad's toppling, the new social contract is still in the making, and trust is wearing down.

Social contracts create “a degree of certainty in the expectations of all involved parties [here: society and the state] about what they must give and receive” (Loewe et al. 2024, 2). Such contracts underpin trust between the parties and stabilize state-society relations. Whereas the Asad-era social contract was placed from above on the people, Asad's fall is a critical juncture that offers a potential for change where a social contract could truly be negotiated between the society and the state. I argue that for a new social contract that does not rely on violence to emerge, trust between the state and the people needs to be created first.

¹ A social contract, along which people's subjugation and/or loyalty was traded for social services and public employment existed, at least in theory, as well, but began to increasingly erode after Bashar al-Asad took power and commenced neoliberal economic policies.

Thus, while Syrians are facing yet another uncertain situation, they need to learn to trust each other. Trust between the ruler and the people needs to be renegotiated in the post-Asad society. Based on their history during the uprising and war, it will not be easy, although it is not an impossible task. Until now, the new rulers have shown trust mainly through words, and they have yet to demonstrate it in action. Without it, it will be difficult for individuals to trust the new authorities and commit to a social contract. If violent and authoritarian practices continue, distrust will likely increase. I analyze here two concerning processes, one related to increasingly centralized powers and the other a form of coercive rule, that have hampered people's trust in the new ruler and have the potential to rapidly undermine the fragile rebuilding of the nation.

Coercion and violence, “a modality of government” that structured and ordered relations between the Syrian rulers and the people (Ismail 2018), was a central tool for the authoritarian regimes of Hafiz (1970–2000) and Bashar al-Asad (2000–2024).¹ While political powers were centralized in the president and the Ba'ath party, the four different intelligence services managed a bureaucracy

of torture, and through surveillance monitored the society (Akdedian 2024, 57). Trust between the ruler and the ruled – or among the people – was not part of the social contract; instead, mistrust was used for the regime to stay in power: ordinary people were recruited as informants, and anyone could be imprisoned without trial and face severe torture and death. Hence, trust existed only among small, intimate networks: family and friends.

After the Syrian uprising erupted in early 2011, local forms of trust emerged among people. This was remarkable as the authoritarian regime had for decades used the authoritarian tools of divide and rule. For activists taking part in the revolution, networks of trust expanded and took new forms; friends of friends got to know each other, and revolutionary activists came together and organized for a common goal: toppling the Asad regime.

As the uprising militarized and the war went on, armed groups became more and more powerful and, again, violence became the mode of governance: mass violence orchestrated by the regime was avenged with violence on perceived loyalist communities; movement was controlled by armed groups, preventing travel for many; and economic activities were increasingly supervised by those with arms. Trust played a role in some of these networks as well, when military groups used their familiar networks to recruit, or when civilians used their intimate links to fighters to carve out space for nonviolent action. Following the uprising's militarization, Syria split into several parts. The divisions were not only entirely based on sectarian lines, although these were intentionally emphasized by different parties, fuelling sectarian tensions and grievances which now have

to be mended.

After Bashar al-Asad was overthrown, many celebrated the end of his violent, authoritarian rule. The interim president, Ahmed al-Sharaa, although originating from an Islamist armed group, Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS), has tried to gain people's trust by emphasizing unity and that the new Syria "is for all Syrians" (Al Jazeera 2025). Since December 2024, Damascus has worked, and on many occasions, succeeded in having sanctions imposed on Syria lifted and in improving the living conditions through new commercial and energy agreements with regional countries. While material reconstruction is important, it alone will not create the trust that is needed between ruler and ruled. Although many of those revolutionary activists that mobilized in 2011 did not support HTS during the war, they remained optimistic that things could turn out better than under Asad. However, for many members of religious and ethnic minorities, potential Islamist rule generated fears of an uncertain future.

Besides rehabilitating foreign policy and the economy, the transitional government is drafting the new social contract, too. It has created political institutions in a rapid manner, before any real nationwide discussions on the topics. The transitional constitution, decreed without public consultation or elections, gives extensive powers to the president, for example, the right to appoint a third of the People's Assembly's members directly. In addition, it fails to create accountability mechanisms and lacks judicial independence (Enab Baladi 2025). Such powers, in force for a five-year transitional period, could cement al-Sharaa's rule beyond this period and ease the return to authoritarian rule. Syrian political thinker Yassin al-Haj Saleh has called such centering of powers "centralist extremist

tendencies” (Al-Haj Saleh 2025).

On a more symbolic level, the president revealed the new emblem for Syria, a gold-en eagle, which symbolizes the unity of the country and the new contract between the people and the state. This amendment, too, was done in closed circles. These changes show how the transitional authorities are already making profound changes on practical and symbolic levels and creating a new Syria of *their* vision. If powers are concentrated in the hands of a small clique, reminiscent of the Asad-era regime, sharing those powers later on will be difficult.

Despite the severity of these changes, a more serious problem has been the large-scale violence that minorities, especially, have faced. The violent events on the coast in March 2025 where over 1600 people, most of them 'Alawites, were killed (Syrian Network for Human Rights 2025a) decreased the little (if any) trust minorities had towards the new rulers, increasing fear that all minorities might be victims of violence in the future.

Some of those fears materialized in July when clashes broke out in as-Sweida governorate initially between local Bedouin tribes and Druze groups. The Syrian General Security was sent to the area to restore order, but many saw this as Damascus’s attempt to coercively take over the governorate, and violence increased. During the first eleven days, over 800 people, civilians and fighters, were killed (Syrian Network for Human Rights 2025b). Adding a regional dimension to the fighting, Israel claimed to protect the Druze and conducted air strikes against General Security forces in Sweida and sites in Damascus. All parties have been accused of violations, and Damascus has ordered an investigation into the events (Danon and Al Nofal 2025). What

is also damning for the new rulers are the human rights violations that their own forces (and fighters with unmarked military attire) have committed – after all, government forces should protect citizens. As had been the case with earlier violent instances, this time authorities cannot claim that their unruly supporters were behind the atrocities. In this instance, President al-Sharaa endorsed large-scale tribal mobilization, which only increased violence (Pinfold and Hammoud 2025). Furthermore, reports of besieged Sweida city bring back images of Asad-style collective punishments of restive areas.

Events in Sweida and the government’s use of coercive power resemble the wartime practices of how power and order were created and preserved, and are darkly reminiscent of Asad-era modes of governance. The events have changed how many ordinary Syrians who want to work for the new country see the new rulers. It can clearly be seen as a watershed moment for post-Asad Syria that has polarized the country further along sectarian and regional lines.

The opposite of trust is distrust. It can manifest as fear or anger, simmering beneath the surface, or in open and violent ways. There are large amounts of weapons available in Syria, and during the war, many disputes were settled with arms. Therefore, if trust is not built, violence can, and will, remain an essential part of the social norms through which communities navigate post-Asad realities. If violence is the means through which communities are ruled and individuals seek to protect themselves against that violence, then Syria will not be united and could even spiral into a renewed and unfettered conflict.

Just as experiences and memories of violence affected ruler-ruled relations and those be-

tween the people during the Asad eras (Ismail 2018, 22), so do wartime and postwar experiences and memories construct relations that are (re)built now. The events of Sweida have shown that transition into a new Syria cannot happen either top down or by force. The rulers have to build trust through their actions, for example, by better including the people in the statebuilding process, investigating violent events in a transparent manner, and holding those who have committed violations accountable. Everyone needs to be included in the making of the new social contract. Alongside this, the security forces need to provide real security to all. But conventional security sector reform alone will never be sufficient. Supporting local initiatives that rebuild communities and create trust between individuals is the crucial step; from this basis, a genuine engagement between ruler and ruled can be built. The importance of trust is manifest and should be central to the process of Syrian reconstruction and statebuilding, but it is a slow, painstaking, and deliberate process that requires dialogue, empathy, understanding, and solidarity. ♦

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